

Did the UK Quality and Outcomes Framework (QOF) pay-for-performance programme improve quality of primary care?

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Background

How to improve quality of care is a challenge shared by all healthcare systems. Many approaches to this challenge have tried, but since the late 1990s there has been considerable interest in using ‘pay-for-performance’, where individual clinicians or organisations are financially incentivized by linking part of their income to how they perform on various measures of quality of care (‘quality indicators’). One of the largest examples of a pay-for-performance system is the Quality and Outcomes Framework (QOF) introduced across the UK as part of the 2004 new contract for general practice (GP).

QOF was unprecedented in its scale and scope. Approximately one-fifth of GP income was tied to performance measured by ~150 quality indicators. These were a mix of clinical indicators relating to care for common long-term conditions, and structural indicators relating to how care was organised. Over time, QOF has changed in various ways. Some quality indicators were retired (ie no longer linked to payment), and new quality indicators were introduced. In 2014, a large number of indicators were retired across the UK, and in 2016 Scotland abolished QOF altogether. The aim of this paper was to understand whether QOF pay-for-performance improved quality of care when payments for higher quality (financial incentives) were introduced, and whether recorded quality got worse when financial incentives were withdrawn.

What did we do?

This study reviewed all published research papers examining what happened to quality of care one year and three years after QOF financial incentives were introduced, and one and three years after they were withdrawn. We examined impact by using data over time to predict what would have happened to quality if QOF had *not* been introduced. QOF impact at one and three years was then measured as the difference between predicted quality and what actually happened. In total, we had data for the impact of introducing financial incentives on 83 quality indicators, and for the impact of withdrawing financial incentives on 31 indicators. Data for 19 indicators which were not incentivised were used to see if pay-for-performance reduced quality for aspects of care not included in QOF.

What did we find?

Compared to what we predicted based on prior trends, financial incentives *improved* recorded quality of care one year later (see figure). The median improvement was 6.1%, but the range of improvement was wide. However, improvements were smaller at three years (median improvement only 0.7%) suggesting that any impact was relatively short-lived. Improvements were largest for indicators where performance before incentivisation was lower, suggesting that for at least some indicators, there was limited room for improvement anyway. When incentives were withdrawn, then recorded quality of care got *worse* at both one year and three years (median change at three years was a reduction of 12.8%).

The biggest changes for both introduction and withdrawal were for recording of processes of care (for example, whether people with heart attack had their blood pressure recorded). Observed impacts were smaller for intermediate outcomes (for example, whether blood pressure was well controlled) and smaller still for treatments (for example, whether people with heart attack were prescribed aspirin).

Key findings

- **QOF is one of the largest healthcare pay-for-performance programmes ever implemented**
- **We reviewed QOF impact on >120 quality indicators**
- **Incentive introduction did improve recorded quality of care at one year, but less so at three years**
- **When incentives were withdrawn, recorded quality of care got worse, reversing any gains**
- **There was some evidence that quality of care for other conditions got slightly worse when QOF was introduced**
- **Conclusion: QOF did not appear to drive sustained improvement in quality of care**

For indicators that were never incentivised, quality of care was unchanged at one year, but slightly worse at three years (average reduction of 1.9%) consistent with other aspects of care possibly being “crowded out” by the focus on QOF.

Figure 1: summary of impact of incentive introduction and withdrawal

Median = the middle value in each group. Half of all datapoints in each group lie within the interquartile range (IQR)

What are the implications of this study?

QOF financial incentives did improve recorded quality of care after one year, but less consistently by three years (although this may partly have been because some indicators were near maximum performance before QOF). Any improvements seemed to be reversed when financial incentives were withdrawn. QOF pay-for-performance did not therefore seem to have a sustained impact on quality of care. However, it isn't easy to tell if observed impacts on recorded quality are due to changes in recording of care versus changes in the actual care received by patients. Equally, there is some evidence that attention paid to QOF 'crowded out' attention to other aspects of quality. This highlights a key dilemma for anyone implementing pay-for-performance: how best to know if overall quality of care delivered to patients improves. Pay-for-performance implementers should therefore carefully consider whether they need a holistic and/or independent evaluation of impact beyond what is recorded in the payment system.

These findings are consistent with previous smaller studies of incentive introduction done in other countries and other settings, and with the few other studies of incentive withdrawal. Despite high hopes when they were introduced, even a pay-for-performance programme as large as QOF did not appear to improve quality of care in a sustained way. One reason may have been that quality was already high for many of the indicators, meaning there was relatively limited scope for improvement.

There is evidence that numerous other types of intervention improve quality (at least in the short-term), including clinical guidelines, education and training, rapid-cycle improvement methods, and support to reorganise care. Quality improvement will often require a mix of improvement methods consistently applied over time. Based on this study and other research about QOF, financial incentives did seem to focus practice's attention and change clinician behaviour at least initially. Although it remains uncertain how best to improve quality of care in a sustained way, it probably needs the use of multiple improvement methods including guidelines, education and training, support to reorganise how care is delivered and (maybe) financial incentives to focus attention.

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